

Table 1. Grain yield and other plant characters of the main crop of IR9784-2-3-2 as affected by N application. IRRI, 1980 wet season.

Basal	Treatment (kg N/ha)				Plant characters ^a					
	Panicle initiation	Early milk stage	Late milk stage	7 days before harvest	Grain yield (t/ha)	Tillers (no./m ²)	Panicles (no./hill)	Filled grains (no./panicle)	100-grain weight (g)	
60	30	0	0	0	3.6	425	16	49	2.2	
30	30	30	0	0	3.5	415	15	46	2.2	
30	30	0	30	0	3.7	448	16	43	2.1	
30	30	0	0	30	3.6	439	15	48	2.1	

^aAv of 4 replications. Analysis of variance showed no difference between treatments at 5% probability level.

higher percentage of missing hills than harvesting at 15 cm or by ani-ani (Table 2). At 5 cm, panicles per hill or per unit area were less than for other treatments. Difference in grain yields was not statistically significant. Plants cut at 5 cm height had more healthy ratoon tillers, heavier grains, and more even maturity than other treatments. They matured in 74 days versus 65 days for 15 cm and 69 days for ani-ani. □

Table 2. Grain yield and other plant characters of a ratoon crop of IR9784-2-3-2 as affected by cutting height of main crop. IRRI, July 1980-January 1981.

Cutting height (cm)	Plant character ^a					
	Grain yield (t/ha)	Productive tillers (no./m ²)	Panicles (no./hill)	Missing hills (%)	Field duration (days)	100-grain weight (%)
5	0.6a	237 b	10 b	7.0a	74a	2.2a
15	0.5a	323a	13a	5.2 b	65 c	2.1 b
ani-ani fb 15 cm	0.6a	316a	13a	3.8 b	69 b	2.2a

^aAv of 4 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level. Also an average of all N treatments. fb = followed by.

Azolla application and rice crop response in Tamil Nadu

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Azolla is a water fern that fixes nitrogen (N) in association with N-fixing blue-green alga *Anabaena azollae*. Four field

experiments were conducted during 1981-82 samba (Oct-Feb). IR20 (at Coimbatore), Bhavani (Ahyarnagar), IR20 (Tirurkuppam), and Ponni (Ambasamudrum) were evaluated using treatments described in the table.

Grain yield for all treatments was higher than for the untreated control. Plots treated with 30 kg N/ha and 30 kg N/ha as azolla at 40 × 10 cm spacing had maximum grain yield followed by plots treated with 60 kg N/ha at 20 × 20 cm spacing at

Aliyarnagar center (see table). A similar trend was observed at Ambasamudrum center, but at Tirurkuppam center plots treated with 60 kg N/ha at 30 × 20 cm spacing had maximum grain yield. At Coimbatore, maximum grain yield was for plots with azolla incorporation as green manure before planting and azolla grown twice as dual crop until heading. Results clearly show the positive influence of azolla inoculation in increasing grain yield. □

Rice crop response to azolla, Tamil Nadu, 1982.

Treatments ^a	Yield (t/ha)							
	Coimbatore		Ambasamudrum		Aliyarnagar		Tirurkuppam	
	IR20	% increase	Ponni	% increase	Bhavani	% increase	IR20	% increase
Uninoculated control, 20 × 20 cm	2.7	—	3.2	—	1.9	—	1.9	—
60 kg N/ha, 20 × 20 cm	4.3	59	3.9	21	2.9	54	2.9	52
60 kg N/ha, 40 × 10 cm	4.1	52	3.9	21	2.7	43	2.7	44
30 kg N/ha by azolla + 30 kg N/ha, 20 × 20 cm	4.3	58	3.8	18	2.7	45	2.4	25
30 kg N/ha by azolla + 30 kg N/ha, 40 × 10 cm	4.2	53	4.0	23	2.9	55	2.4	29
Azolla GM + azolla DC, 20 × 20 cm	4.4	64	3.7	14	2.6	38	2.6	36
Azolla GM + azolla DC, 40 × 10 cm	4.1	51	3.5	9	2.4	27	2.4	29
Azolla DC, 40 × 10 cm	4.1	50	3.4	3	2.5	32	2.5	35

C.D. = 497

C.D. = 387

C.D. = 910

C.D. = 210

^aGM = green manure, DC = dual crop. N was applied as 3 splits. *Azolla pinnata* was inoculated at 300 g/m² on the 7th day after planting.